

Maternal Mortality in Nepal: Progress, Persistent Gaps, and Reliability (2021-2025)

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Abstract—*Maternal mortality remains a critical health issue in Nepal despite substantial progress. This structured review synthesizes recent national reports, peer-reviewed literature, and official surveillance updates (2021–2025) to assess trends, persistent challenges, and data reliability. Nepal’s maternal mortality ratio (MMR) has declined from 539 per 100,000 live births in 1996 to about 142 in recent estimates, with the National Statistics Office reporting 151 for 2021. Progress aligns with Safe Motherhood initiatives and Family Welfare Division services; however, underreporting and partial surveillance—active MPDSR in only 51 of 77 districts—limit confidence in recent counts. Achieving the national target (MMR 99) requires nationwide MPDSR coverage, transparent data verification, and equity-focused investments in access and quality of care.*

Keywords- *Maternal Mortality Rate, Surveillance, Data Reliability, Nepal, Sustainable Development Goal (SDG)*

1. INTRODUCTION

Maternal mortality—death of a woman during pregnancy or within 42 days of termination of pregnancy—remains a critical but often neglected in developing countries. Analyzing complications, management issues, and facility challenges is difficult due to poor data recording [1]. According to World Health Organization (WHO) approximately 287,000 women died from maternal causes worldwide in 2020, representing a 34- 40% decline since 2000, largely due to improved access to essential health services.

Nepal, like many low- and middle-income countries, continues to face challenges in both reducing and accurately estimating its maternal mortality burden. The national Maternal Mortality Ratio (MMR) was estimated at 139 per 100,000 live births in 2022, with a slight variation to 142 per 100,000 in 2023 [2]. While this reflects progress over the past two decades, the fluctuations also suggest potential issues with underreporting and data incompleteness.

Multiple factor contribute to maternal deaths in Nepal, including limited access to healthcare,

inadequate nutrition, poor transportation infrastructure, a shortage of qualified healthcare professionals, and low community awareness. Although reported data suggests a declining trend in the MMR, concerns regarding underreporting, incomplete data, and overall reliability challenge the validity of this progress. A clear examination of the influencing factors, data quality, and healthcare facilities is necessary [3].

This study aims to identify key factors associated with maternal mortality in Nepal, evaluate incomplete data and accuracy of recorded maternal mortality and assess the extent to which government health facilities and community knowledge have influenced maternal mortality trends.

Fig 1: source (macrotrends.net)

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Global and National Context

Maternal health remains a critical global health priority. In 2023, approximately 260,000 women died from pregnancy-related causes, with a disproportionate 92% of these deaths occurring in low- and middle-income countries [4]. The majority of these deaths are considered preventable. Globally, significant progress has been made, with substantial declines in the maternal mortality ratio (MMR) in regions such as Sub-Saharan Africa, Northern Africa, and Western Asia [5].

Nepal exemplifies this global progress. Current data indicate a substantial decline in Nepal's MMR from a critical baseline of 539 deaths per 100,000 live births in 1996 to an estimated 142 in 2023. This aligns closely with the National Statistics Office's report of 151 per 100,000 live births in 2021, which was derived from census and verbal autopsy data. Aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Nepal has established national targets to reduce its MMR further, aiming for 99 by 2025.

Fig 2: source (genderdata.worldbank.org)

B. Historical Challenges: The “Three Delays” Model

Nepal's journey in reducing maternal mortality involved addressing deep-rooted systemic and social issues [3], often analyzed through the “Three Delays” [5].

- **The First Delay:** Delay in seeking care often due to limited awareness of danger signs, lack of education, lack of information, socio-cultural barriers that prevent women from making timely decisions about seeking medical attention.
- **The Second Delay:** Delay in reaching a healthcare facility due to geographical difficulties, poor roads, and long travel times from rural and remote areas to health centers [6].
- **The Third Delay:** Delay in receiving proper care after arriving at a facility. This is caused by a lack of professional healthcare providers, lack of essential equipment and

drugs, and inconsistent quality of care.

These challenges are more acute for women from poorer households, who have historically had less access to quality maternal healthcare [5].

C. Persistent Challenges and Current initiatives

MMR trends shows a gradual decline over the past few decades, although significant challenges remain [7]. The Government of Nepal health services such as the Safe Motherhood Programme, Aama Surakshya Scheme, and the Family Welfare Division's free institutional services have played crucial role in this reduction in maternity mortality.

Each year, funds is allocated to The Family Welfare Division under the department of health services [8].

Approximately 40% of deliveries still occur at home, driven by geographic inaccessibility, cultural practices, and the persistent challenges of the “Three Delays” model. Clinical complications such as postpartum hemorrhage and social factor including child marriage and teenage pregnancies continue to contribute to maternal deaths and increase vulnerability [6].

D. Data Recording and Quality of Maternal Mortality Data in Nepal

A critical emerging issue in assessing Nepal's progress is the reliability of Maternal Mortality data. Although Nepal has made remarkable progress in reducing maternal mortality from 539 deaths per 100,000 live births in 1996 to 142 in 2023, experts caution that this improvement may not fully reflect in the ground due to underreporting and incomplete surveillance [9].

According to the Family Welfare Division (FWD), only 150 maternal deaths in fiscal year 2080/2081 and 2081/2082 which is the lowest figure ever recorded [11]. However, this data was collected from only 51 districts that operate an active Maternal and Perinatal Death Surveillance and Response (MPDSR) system, leaving 26 districts unmonitored. Consequently, health experts argue that the current statistics are not nationally representative and likely underestimate true mortality rates [10]. Figure 1

Figure 2. Distribution of Maternal Deaths Reported from hospitals and Community (N=240)

Fig 3: source (fwd.gov.np)

Experts have emphasized the need to strengthen the MPDSR mechanism, expand it to all 77 districts, and ensure regular data verification. As Dr. Gautam noted that Nepal should first fix the recording and reporting system before celebrating success. Without accurate and transparent data, it remains difficult to evaluate progress or design effective policy interventions [11].

3. METHODOLOGY

This research includes a descriptive and analytical research design based exclusively on a systematic review of secondary data. The primary objective of the methodology is to gather most recent and relevant information of maternity mortality in Nepal, with a specific focus on trends, data quality and influencing factors covering the period from 2021 to 2025, with a focus on trends, data reliability, and influencing factors related to maternal mortality in Nepal.

A. Research Design and Data Collection

The data collection process was structured to prioritize contemporary sources. A systematic search was conducted across Academic databases, including Google Scholar using a structured set of keywords: “maternal mortality ratio Nepal,” “Maternal mortality Nepal.”

The review incorporated the following source types to ensure a comprehensive perspective:

- **International Reports:** WHO reports and fact sheets.
- **National Survey and Data:** The Nepal Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS) 2022 [9] and reports from the National Statistics Office [5].
- **Government Publication:** Policy documents, program details, and surveillance reports from the Government of Nepal’s Ministry of Health and population and the Family Welfare Division (FWD).

- **Academic Literature:** Peer-reviewed journal articles investigating maternal health outcome and challenges in Nepal.
- **News Media:** Investigate article “The Kathmandu Post” to capture real-time opinions and emerging data debates.

B. Analytical Framework and Variables

The analysis was guided by framework that examined the relationships between multiple variables affecting maternal mortality.

1. Variable Identification

- **Dependent Variable:**
The Maternal Mortality Ratio (MMR) and the completeness and accuracy of its reporting.
- **Independent Variable:**
 - **Health System Factors**
 - **Socioeconomic and Cultural Factors**
 - **Data Quality and Governance Factors**

2. Comparative Analysis

- **Cross-source comparison:** Compared WHO, NDHS and FWD data to check consistency.
- **Trend analysis:** Studied changes in MMR over time.
- **Geographic Comparison:** Looked at difference between districts and MPDSR coverage.

The collected data were synthesized and analyzed. The focus was on critically evaluating the accuracy and completeness of recorded maternal mortality data. As this study relied exclusively on publicly available secondary data, no primary data collection involving human subjects was conducted.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The analysis of national data, news reports and research paper indicates that Nepal has achieved significant reduction in its MMR over the past two decades, WHO reporting a rate of 142 per 100,000 live births in 2023 which is a 71 percent decline since 2000. This progress positions the country closer to its national target of 99 by 2025 and the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) of 70 by 2030. Government programs such as the Safe Motherhood Programs and free institutional delivery services are widely acknowledged as major contributors to the decline.

Year	Data type and Source	MMR (per 100,000 live births)	Notes
1996	NFHS baseline (survey)	539 MMR	Historical baseline
2021	National Statistics Office (modeled)	151 MMR	Modeled national estimate [11].
2023	WHO Global Estimates (modeled)	142 MMR	WHO statistical estimate.
2023/2024 (FY 2080/81)	Family Welfare Division (raw count)	150 deaths counted (not an MMR) (only 51/77 districts)	MPDSR active in 51/77 districts; not nationally complete [3].

Table 1: Nepal's Maternal Mortality Estimates and Official Government Reports

A. Critical Discussion: Interpreting the Decline and Data Reliability

While the reported trend is positive, a critical examination reveals that this progress is threatened by fundamental weakness in the health system and mostly, notably, in data surveillance. The core issue is the interpretation of the declining MMR.

Policymakers risk celebrating a statistical success that may not fully reflect the on-the-ground reality, leading to complacency and misallocation of resources. A primary concern is the reliability of the data itself.

As shown in Table 1, while modeled estimate show decline, the most recent count of only 150 maternal deaths for the 2024/25 fiscal year is drawn solely from the 51 districts with an active MPDSR system. This leaves 26 districts without systematic monitoring. Consequently health experts question the accuracy of this count. This data gap directly undermines the ability to formulate targeted, effective policies, as it is impossible to solve a problem that is not being fully measured.

The well-documented “Three Delays” model provides the context for why the official data may be an undercount. These delays are exacerbated by critical

shortage of skilled health workers, a lack of essential equipment, and complicated emergency referral system [4]. When a death occurs in a remote, unmonitored district due to these delays, it is less likely to be captured in the official system. Therefore, the “declining” MMR may not only reflect genuine improvement but also the systematic exclusion of the most vulnerable populations who face the greatest barriers to care. Clinical complication such as postpartum hemorrhage and pre-eclampsia remain leading causes of death, and their true incidence is masked by this incomplete data [12].

Ultimately, insufficient and declining funding for maternal health programs risks reversing the progress made. To secure a sustainable path forward, Nepal must prioritize strengthening the MPDSR system to fulfill national coverage. This is not just a statistical exercise but a fundamental prerequisite for accurate analysis, and ultimately saving lives. Strategic investment must be directed both to the health workforce and infrastructure and to the surveillance system itself to ensure that success is real and measurable, not just reported.

Figure 16: Complications during postpartum period (N=376)

Figure 22: Perception of delays in health facility (N=611)

Fig 4: source (censusnepal.cbs.gov.np)

Figure 20: Venn diagram depicting three delays (N=611)

Fig 5: source (censusnepal.cbs.gov.np)

5. CONCLUSION

To achieve that Sustainable Development Goal of reducing the maternal mortality ratio to below 70 per 100,000 live births by 2030 Nepal must put efforts with a focused and multi-pronged strategy. While official reports indicates a commendable decline in maternal mortality over recent decades, ensuring the accuracy of this data itself is paramount. This requires expanding the MPDSR system to every district to guarantee complete and reliable reporting which is the foundation for effective action.

Furthermore, sustained progress is connected on strategic and transparent financial investment. Funding designated for maternal health must be managed effectively and its allocation and expenditure should made public to ensure accountability and maximize impact. Beyond financial measures, it is critical to address the stark inequities in care. This involves strengthening health infrastructure in rural and remote areas, providing quality preconception and antenatal education, and ensuring all women, especially those from poor communities, receive equitable and respectful care in hospital and society.

Ultimately, the path forward demands continuous investment, monitoring and strong public awareness campaigns. Continued collaboration between the government, local health systems, communities, and data agencies will be the key to achieving SDG 3.1. By strengthening health systems, improving data transparency and ensuring equitable access to quality

care, Nepal can safeguard the gains made and accelerate progress toward ensuring safe motherhood for all women.

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